

Study on “Fixed Points” for OWC in Symmetric Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, we obtain a unique common fixed point theorem for OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible) four self- mappings in symmetric spaces. This result is a generalization, improving, extending, known comparable results existing in the literature.

Key words: Common fixed point theorem, OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible), Symmetric space.

AMS Subject Classifications: 47H10, 54H25.

1. Introduction

We know that Banach contraction principle (prior to 1968) is a fundamental result in fixed point theory. Later on Kannan [14] obtained a fixed point result for a mapping satisfying contractive condition that need not satisfy continuity. Subsequently many authors has been extended and improved and generalizes these result in many ways (see for e.g. [1-13] and [15-18]). Hicks and Rhoades [10] obtained some common fixed point theorems in symmetric spaces and semi metric spaces. Recently, Abbas and Rhoades [6] obtained some common fixed point results for occasionally weakly compatible mappings satisfying a generalized contractive condition in symmetric spaces. In this paper we obtained a common fixed point theorem for OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible) four self- mappings in symmetric spaces. Our results are more general than the several well known results.

1.1. Preliminaries

The following are useful in our main results which are due to [6].

Definition 1.1. Two maps p and q are said to be weakly compatible if they commute at coincidence points.

Definition 1.2. Let X be a set , p, q self maps of X . A point x in X is called a coincidence point of p and q iff $px = qx$. We shall call $w = px = qx$ a point of coincidence of p and q .

Definition 1.3. Two self maps p, q of a set X . A point x in X are said to be OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible) iff there exists a point x in X which is a coincidence point of p and q at which p and q are commute.

Lemma 1.1 (11). *Let X be a set , p, q are OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible) self maps of X . If p and q have a unique point coincidence $w = px = qx$, then w is a unique common fixed point of p and q .*

Our results are proved in symmetric spaces, which are more general than metric spaces.

Definition 1.4. Let X be a set. A symmetric on X is a mapping $\rho(x, y) : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that $\rho(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$, and $\rho(x, y) = \rho(y, x)$ for $x, y \in X$.

Let $A \in [0, \infty)$, $R_A^+ = [0, A)$. Let $F : R_A^+ \rightarrow R$ satisfy

(i). $F(0) = 0$ and $F(t) > 0$ for each $t \in (0, A)$ and (ii). F is non decreasing on R_A^+ .

Define, $F[0, A) = \{F : R_A^+ \rightarrow R : F \text{ satisfies (i) - (ii)}\}$. Let $A \in [0, \infty)$. Let $\Psi : R_A^+ \rightarrow R$ satisfies (i). $\Psi(t) < t$ for each $t \in (0, A)$ and (ii). Ψ is non decreasing.

Define, $\Psi[0, A) = \{\Psi : R_A^+ \rightarrow R : \Psi \text{ satisfies (i) - (ii) above}\}$.

Some of the examples of mappings $F : R_A^+ \rightarrow R : F$ satisfies (i) - (ii), we have refer to [17].

Definition 1.5. A control function Φ defined by $\Phi : R^+ \rightarrow R^+$ which satisfies $\Phi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$.

2. Main Results

In this section, we proved a unique common fixed point theorem for four self-mappings for OWC(Occasionally Weakly Compatible) mappings in symmetric spaces.

Now we prove our main theorem.

Theorem 2.1. Let X be a set, ρ a symmetric on X . Let M, N, S and T be four self-mappings of X satisfying the following conditions:

$$F(\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))) < \Psi(F(K_\Phi(u, v))), \quad (1)$$

where,

$$K_\Phi(u, v) = \text{Max}\{\lambda_1[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Tv)) + \Phi(\rho(Su, Mu)) + \Phi(\rho(Nv, Tv)))] + \text{Max}\{\lambda_2[\Phi(\rho(Mu, Tv)) + \Phi(\rho(\frac{Su, Nv}{2}))]\}\}.$$

Where, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ and $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 < 1$.

For each $u, v \in X$, $F \in F[0, B)$ and $\Psi \in \Psi[0, F((B - 0))$, where $B = D$ if $D = \infty$ and $B > D$ if $D < \infty$. And

$$(M, S) \text{ and } (N, T) \text{ are OWC.} \quad (2)$$

Then M, N, S and T are having a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof. Given by (2) (M, S) and (N, T) are OWC, then there exists two points $u, v \in X$ such that $Mu = Su$ and $Nv = Tv$. For suppose that $Mu \neq Nv$. Then from (1) we get that,

$$\begin{aligned} K_\Phi(u, v) &= \text{Max}\{\lambda_1[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Nv)) + \Phi(\rho(Mu, Mu)) + \Phi(\rho(Tv, Tv)))] + \text{Max}\{\lambda_2[\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv)) + \Phi(\rho(\frac{Mu, Nv}{2}))]\}\}, \\ &= \text{Max}\{\lambda_1[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Nv)) + \Phi(\rho(0)) + \Phi(\rho(0)))] + \text{Max}\{\lambda_2[\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv)) + \Phi(\rho(\frac{Mu, Nv}{2}))]\}\}, \\ &= \text{Max}\{\lambda_1[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Nv)))] + \text{Max}\{\lambda_2[\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))]\}\}, \\ &= \lambda_1[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Nv)))] + \lambda_2[\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))], \\ &= (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)[\Phi(\rho((Mu, Nv)))] \text{, (since } \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 < 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$< \Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv)). \quad (3)$$

Then from (1) and (3) we get that ,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < F(\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))) &< \Psi(F(K_{\Phi}(u, v))) \\ &< \Psi(F(\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))), \\ &< F(\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv))), \text{ which is a contradiction.} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\Phi(\rho(Mu, Nv)) = 0$.

$$\implies \rho(Mu, Nv) = 0.$$

$$\implies Mu = Nv. \text{ That is, } Mu = Su = Nv = Tv.$$

Suppose that if there exists another point z such that $Mz = Sz$, then using (1) and (3) we get that $Mz = Sz = Nv = Tv = Mu = Su$ or $Mu = Mz$ and $w = Mu = Su$ is the unique point of M and S . By Lemma (1.1) , w is the only common fixed point of M and S . By symmetry there exists a unique point $z \in X$ such that $z = Nz = Tz$. Suppose that $w \neq z$ then by (1) and (3) we get that,

$$\begin{aligned} F(\Phi(\rho(w, z))) = F(\Phi(\rho(Mw, Nz))) &< \Psi(F(K_{\Phi}(w, z))) \\ &< \Psi(F(\Phi(\rho(w, z)))) \\ &< F(\Phi(\rho(w, z))), \text{ which is a contradiction.} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\Phi(\rho(w, z)) = 0$.

$$\implies \rho(w, z) = 0.$$

$$\implies w = z.$$

Therefore, $w = z$ is a common fixed point. By the preceding argument and it is clear that w is the unique. Therefore, M , N , S and T are having a unique common fixed point in X . And this completes the proof of the theorem. \square

3. Conclusion

Our results are more general than the results of [6].

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